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Disproportionation of 4-Hydroxyazobenzene and Interaction with Copper(I)

P. N. GUPTA* and ANJU RAINA

Department of Chemistry, University of Kashmir, Srinagar-190 006

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THE reduction of 4-hydroxyazobenzene at low concentration (for obvious reasons of maintaining the monomeric form¹ of the dye in solution) in Clark and Lubs (KH₂PO₄ and NaOH) buffer of pH 5.8-8.0 containing 1 M KCl at the dme gave a single well defined diffusion-controlled wave. The acidic ionisation constant of the compound was 6.7 × 10⁻⁸ under the experimental conditions and varies very slightly (pK_a 7.17 to 7.16) over the concentration range of 0.1-1.0 mM. The E_{1/2} values shifted linearly with the change in pH according to the following equation,

$$E_{1/2} = 0.08 - 0.07 \text{ pH}$$

The determined value of potential, E⁰ was -0.332 V at pH 6.5 which differed from the calculated value by -0.043 V, providing information that the reduction was not reversible. The substituent constants (ρ=0.14 and Σσ=-0.37) were in confirmation with the work of various authors^{2,3}. Several mechanistic pathways have been highlighted earlier^{4,5} for the reduction of azo compounds. The proposed scheme (Scheme 1) of simultaneous protonation and electron transfer process, followed by slow electron attack to form radical (IV) and anion (III) is attributed to disproportionation reaction, presumably due to the strong electron attracting tendency of -OH in the moiety. Depending on the medium, the different set of products would be obtained,

e.g. in acid, aniline (V) and 4-hydroxyaniline (VI), while in base, the latter is the only product. The possibility of remote reaction cannot be ruled out resulting in 4,4'-dihydroxyhydrazobenzene (VII) and aniline (V) in acid and base media respectively.

Scheme 1. Reduction scheme of 4-hydroxyazobenzene.

The addition of Cu²⁺ (stock solution 0.75 mM) in dye solution (0.1 mM) was made in five steps ranging from 0.125 to 0.25 mM resulted in the following changes in the polarograms: (i) The wave height increased, (ii) E_{1/2} shifted towards more negative potential and (iii) wave shape altered. The procedure was reversed with metal ion in cell while the adequate quantities of 4-hydroxyazobenzene was added. The polarograms showed dissimilar characteristics in the sense that a single composite anodic-cathodic wave⁶ crossing base line at -0.24 V was noticed. This corresponds to the E_{1/2} of the cathodic wave of Cu²⁺ in this medium. The height of cathodic and anodic waves being equal favour disproportionation reaction at the dme. The log plot revealed linearity with a slope + 56 mV which indicates irreversible wave nature of Cu²⁺ in this medium. The calculated E_{a/4} - E_{1/4} resulted in αn=0.923, confirming irreversibility. The above observations indicate complexation.

Disproportionation⁷ of Cu²⁺ to Cu⁰ and Cu⁺ possessing high free energy change is a thermodynamically favourable reaction. This would certainly be induced by ligand which itself is capable of disproportionation. Stability parameters of complexes of Cu²⁺ with the ligand in terms of changes in diffusion coefficient were evaluated by the method developed by Crow⁸, which incorporates the change in diffusion current due to complexation in terms of ligand number, i.e.

$$\Delta i_d \propto n.$$

The technique is applicable to reversible and irreversible processes alike. The difference in i_d values can be measured more accurately, therefore, it is advantageous over the methods which involve $E_{1/2}$ term.

The concentration of ligand bound to metal can be obtained from Bjerrum's treatment⁹ (Table 1),

$$n = (C_x - [x]) / C_M$$

C_x , C_M and $[x]$ are the total ligand, metal and free ligand concentrations, respectively. Calculations from the following expression,

$$\bar{n} = (1 - \bar{n}) \beta_1 [x] + (2 - \bar{n}) \beta_2 [x]^2$$

(by graphical method) gave stability constant β 's in terms of $\bar{n}$ values as $\beta_1 = 15$, $\beta_2 = 1 \times 10^6$, $\beta_3 = 1.6 \times 10^6$ and $\beta_4 = 3.03 \times 10^6$. Similarly, the plots of $\bar{n}$ vs $\log [x]$ is in accordance with Fronaeus integral results in Fo $[x]$ functions. Using these functions the following values of stability constants were obtained, $\beta_1 = 15.1$, $\beta_2 = 1.02 \times 10^6$, $\beta_3 = 1.59 \times 10^6$ and $\beta_4 = 3.01 \times 10^6$. In terms of equilibrium constant of each step it is found

$$\beta_1 = K_1 = 15.1$$

$$\beta_2 = K_1 K_2 = 1.02 \times 10^6$$

$$\beta_3 = K_1 K_2 K_3 = 1.59 \times 10^6$$

$$\beta_4 = K_1 K_2 K_3 K_4 = 3.01 \times 10^6$$

So that $K_2 = 67.5$, $K_3 = 155.8$ and $K_4 = 18.8$, indicating strong complexation in general. Comparing the two methods, the latter set of values seems more precise because of the involvement of exact integral functions. A clear out inflection in the formation curve at $n = 4$ is probably due to Jahn-Teller effect, owing to which first 4 complexes of Cu are more stable. Further, Bjerrum method of corresponding

TABLE 1—LIGAND CONCENTRATION AND FORMATION FUNCTION

$C_x \cdot 10^4$	$[x] \cdot 10^4$	$\bar{n}$	$\bar{n}/[x]$
1.0	0.75	0.025	500
3.0	1.50	0.014	933
5.0	2.5	0.270	1080
7.0	3.0	0.420	1400
10.0	3.8	0.590	1552
20.0	4.5	1.550	3444
30	8.75	2.120	2423
50	19.0	3.100	1613
100	63	3.70	587
200	165	3.95	239
300	260	4.00	154
400	360	4.125	114

solutions is suitable rather for less stable complexes. The hard ligand ($-N=N-$) can suitably interact with hard base Cu to justify high stability constant. The overall stability constant comes out characteristically as 7.37×10^{16} and is quite appropriate considering the type of the system under discussion. The free radical and the anion generated according to step 2 (Scheme 1) would initially be so reactive to interact with metal to present so called acid-base type neutrality. Evidently it would be likely that instead of four stepwise constants, only one

β value could be ascertained. In other words, had there been fast electron attack, the above observation could be envisaged, however, it is not the case. This step could then be designated as slow step. Slow uptake of electron by hydrazo derivative has been depicted earlier¹⁰ to proceed via radical ion formation only in alkaline medium, seems not well founded instead it should be independent of the medium as shown in Scheme 1. Parshall¹¹ during the course of study of metallation of azobenzenes, observed that substituent effect has direct relation with the complex formation reaction and that *para*-substituted molecules are more reactive otherwise as has been observed in this study.

Calculation of free energy changes and other thermodynamic parameters (Table 2) depict that absolute value of ΔG° is increased from 1.546 to

TABLE 2—CALCULATED THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

Temp. °C	β_n	$-\Delta F$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta H$ (Graphically) kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
25	β_1 15.1	1.619		- 7.10
30	β_1 13.6	1.577		- 7.15
35	β_1 12.3	1.546	3.743	- 7.13
25	β_2 1020	4.130		+ 1.00
30	β_2 918	4.135		+ 1.015
35	β_2 826	4.138	3.827	+ 1.01
25	β_3 159000	7.138		+10.41
30	β_3 142000	7.190		+10.41
35	β_3 127000	7.240	4.035	+10.41
25	β_4 3010000	8.892		+16.85
30	β_4 2700000	8.975		+16.85
35	β_4 2430000	9.059	3.868	+16.85

9.059 kcal mol⁻¹, when the ligand number varied from 1 to 4. Complex formation in solution phase reaction favours such observation. Constancy in ΔH values indicates no effect of temperature during complexation (Table 2). Substantial changes in ΔS for the stepwise equilibrium is evident, resulting in $(\Delta S_3 - \Delta S_2) > (\Delta S_2 - \Delta S_1)$, which denotes that the stability constant in a series increases with the ligand number. However, $(\Delta S_4 - \Delta S_3)$ is smaller than either of the two to provide information that further addition of ligand does not affect the equilibrium any more.

A further probe into the complexation nature was worked out from the function¹², $f[x] = \bar{n}/[x]$ (Table 1). The function related to the stability constants by

$$\frac{\bar{n}}{[x]} = \beta_1 + (2\beta_2 - \beta_1^2) [x] + (3\beta_3 - 3\beta_1 \beta_2 + \beta_1^3) [x]^2$$

gives a maximum at about $[x] = 4.5 \times 10^{-4} M$ showing $2\beta_2 > \beta_1^2$ (similarly, $\beta_3 > \beta_1 \beta_2 - \beta_1^3/3$). An inference to this effect is that a relationship, $2K_3 > K_1$ should exist between the formation constants of the first and second complex. The present study proves this beyond doubt. The increase in K_2 value is due to disproportionation step prior to complexation.

In order to describe complexation qualitatively a plot of $\log K_n$ vs $f(\bar{n}-1)$ has been drawn (Fig. 1). The higher values of K_1 and K_3 compared with

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log K_n$ vs $(\bar{n}-1)$.

K_1 primarily reflects the presence of two possible structures, competing with each other. The tendency to form more stable structure (i.e. tetrahedral ones) is evident at ca. $\bar{n}=3$ (Fig. 1). A sudden break indicates the conversion of stabler form into less stable structure which could have been observed at higher coordination number.

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Effect of Ionic Surfactants on the Chromatographic Separation of Phenols

J. P. RAWAT* and ONKAR SINGH

Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University,
Aligarh-202 001

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RECENTLY, the use of micellar systems in analytical techniques have been reviewed¹. However, the use of surfactants has not been tried so far to study the movement of phenols on chro-

matographic papers. In this study we have made use of aqueous micellar (normal micellar) systems of different charge type in the separation of phenols. It is well known that the properties of micelles are drastically changed by the change of environment, hence the effect of alcohols and salts has been studied on the separation of phenols in the presence of such additives in the micellar systems

This paper deals with the paper chromatography of 28 phenols of different types in aqueous sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) and cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB) systems. The effect of addition of propanol and electrolytes (NaCl and KBr) is also studied. The important separations, practically achieved, are reported.

Experimental

Chromatography was performed on Whatman No. 3 paper strips of size 15×3 cm using 20×5 cm glass jars.

Chemicals and solvents were of analytical grade Sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) and cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB) were B. D. H. (England) products, which were further purified by repeated crystallisation from 95% ethanol followed by prolonged extraction from chloroform (100 h) and petroleum ether (60 h) to ensure the complete removal of traces of unreacted alcohol. It was then filtered and dried overnight in an hot air-oven to a constant weight. The purity of the surfactants was ensured from the absence of minimum in the surface tension vs concentration plots. The spotting solutions of phenols were prepared in ethanol. For the detection of various phenols, ferric chloride solution (0.1 M), sodium hydroxide solution (0.1 M) and 1% phosphomolybdic acid solution were used.

Procedure: Phenols were spotted with the help of fine glass capillaries on the strips. The paper was conditioned for 15 min and solvent was then allowed to ascend 11 cm in every case. The R_f values were calculated as usual.

Results

Detection: Phenols were easily detected on chromatograms. For the detection of various phenols, ferric chloride sodium hydroxide and phosphomolybdic acids were used. The variety of colours obtained with various types of phenols are as follows.

Phloroglucinol, catechol, xylenol, bromothymol blue, di(2-hydroxyphenylimino)ethane gave blue coloured spots.

In certain cases the use of sodium hydroxide spray was also made just after spraying ferric chloride to achieve clear detection. The colours observed with known phenols are as follows. *m*-Cresol and *p*-cresol gave brown spots. Resorcinol and gallic acid gave violet spots. 1-Nitroso-2-naphthol gave green spot. Pyrogallol gave blue spot.